

GRAPHITE NANOSHEET 3-D NETWORKS FOR POLYMER COMPOSITES CAPABLE OF ENHANCED HEAT TRANSPORT

Sung Gook Jin¹ and Sang-Soo Lee^{1,2}

¹ Photo-Electronic Hybrids Research Center, Korea Institute of Science and Technology,
Seoul 136-791, Republic of Korea

² KU-KIST Graduate School of Converging Science and Technology, Korea University,
Seoul 136-701, Republic of Korea
Email: s-slee@kist.re.kr, web page: <http://nanohybrids.kist.re.kr>

Keywords: three dimensional interconnected network, graphite nanosheet, nanocomposite, thermal energy transfer

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we prepared 3-D network architecture of graphite nanosheets (GNS) to construct an efficient pathway for the thermal energy transfer in preparing a thermal management composite material. In achieving 3-D GNS network of excellent thermal energy transfer under practically usable condition, GNS filling into the interstitial sites among colloidal polymer particle aggregates and following removal of polymer components were conducted. The voids surrounded by 3-D network of GNS were re-filled out using butylene terephthalate-based cyclic oligomers which were ring-opening polymerized to form a PBT/GNS nanocomposite. The thermal conductivity of the PBT/GNS nanocomposite employing 3-D interconnected GNS content as low as 9 wt% has reached ca. 4.3 W/mK, that is much higher than the case of randomly distributed GNS of comparable amount. The capability of controlling lateral size and thickness of GNS as well as the 3-D macroporous interconnected graphene framework in polymer matrix should greatly assist the commercialization of high-quality graphene-based thermal management materials in a scalable production process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal management of electronic devices is a crucial issue for the development of integrated circuits, three-dimensional (3-D) integration, ultrafast high-power-density communication devices, and so on.[1] Great effort has been devoted to fabricating thermal management materials (TMMs) for use between heat sources and heat sinks to effectively dissipate the heat and maintain a satisfactory operating temperature for the device.[2] As a representative TMM, polymer nanocomposites containing thermally conducting fillers have received considerable attention as thermal management systems because of their ease of fabrication, low cost and low processing temperatures.[3]

Several materials have been studied as fillers in such systems; e.g., metal powders, ceramic particles and carbon-based materials. For metal and ceramic fillers, which include silver, boron nitride and aluminium oxide, a high quantity of filler (ca. 40–60 wt%) is required to achieve percolation thresholds and obtain high thermal conductivities (1–5 W m⁻¹K⁻¹). These needs are met at high cost but the nanocomposites have poor mechanical properties.[4] Some carbon-based materials are attractive alternatives because of their relatively low costs, good mechanical strengths and high surface areas.[5] Graphene has been thought most promising among the carbon-based TMMs because of its remarkable characteristics, such as high thermal conductivity (5000 W m⁻¹K⁻¹) and charge carrier mobility (200,000 cm² V s⁻¹).[6]

Graphene sheets are conventionally prepared by the reduction of chemically exfoliated graphene oxide (GO).[7] However, a small number of unreduced functional groups remain after the reduction; e.g., hydroxyl, carboxyl and epoxide groups on the basal planes and edges, which have been well known to lead to poor thermal and electrical conductivities. Furthermore, local agglomeration and random dispersion of the graphene filler in a polymer matrix causes high phonon scattering, which also deteriorates the thermal conductivity.[8] Additionally, this technology suffers from a time-

consuming exfoliation process and low graphene yield and as a consequence has found only limited commercial applications.[9] Therefore, an efficient and facile strategy for the fabrication of defect-free graphene in large quantities, well-dispersed in a polymer matrix, is needed.

Several researchers have noted that the van der Waals interactions between neighbouring graphene layers may impart a potential as a suitable building block for highly ordered assemblies to that material.[10] In particular, a 3-D nanostructure such as an interconnected mesoporous network of graphene sheets has recently emerged as a promising filler for a polymer matrix because of its ultrahigh surface area, and novel physical and electronic properties, which allows a large contact area with the polymer matrix.[11] In this way, it can efficiently provide percolated pathways for heat transfer at a low filler content, and thereby greatly increases the thermal conductivity of the polymer nanocomposite.

Herein, we report a novel route for the fabrication of a free-standing graphite nanosheet (GNS) embedded film having outstanding thermal conductivity via infiltration of a thermoplastic polymer matrix into the 3-D mesoporous interconnected GNS framework. In order to obtain size-scalable GNS of very few defects which is prerequisite in suppressing phonon scattering, an eco-friendly wet bead milling of pristine graphite has been attempted with no use of toxic and labor-intensive chemical exfoliation. Thermal calcination of the polystyrene (PS) spheres used as a template provided a high packing density and a stability of the 3-D GNS framework, which are critical in enhancing the thermal conductivity. Changes in the thermal conductivities of the PS/GNS mixture, the 3-D interconnected GNS network structure after the PS removal and the 3-D GNS nanocomposite film after polymer filling were examined as a function of the PS spheres diameter, milling time and GNS content, and were compared to that of the composite derived from random mixing of GNS with polymer matrix.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials: The graphite flakes used in the experiments were supplied by Asbury; the mean lateral size and density of the graphite were ca. 100 μm and 2.2 g cm^{-3} , respectively. Cetrimonium bromide ($(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Br})$, CTAB), used as cationic dispersing agent for graphite in water, styrene monomer and potassium persulfate (KPS) with high purity were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich. Cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT) oligomers of extra pure grade were acquired from the Cyclics.

2.2. Fabrication of the GNS via bead milling: Pristine graphite of various amounts was added to deionized water (800 mL) containing 0.1 wt% CTAB, and the slurry solution was placed in a slurry tank. A pump was used to deliver the slurry into a bead-mill reactor with capacity of 200 mL, and flow rate of the slurry was regulated to 10 kg h^{-1} . For effective bead milling, the reactor was charged with 420 g of zirconium oxide beads (diameter: 0.1 mm, density: 5,680 kg m^{-3}) and the rotational speed was adjusted to 3700 rpm. The resultant GNS aqueous suspension was collected as a function of milling time. Centrifugation and washing were employed to remove excess amount of surfactant.

2.3. Synthesis of the PS spheres: PS spheres were fabricated by surfactant-free emulsion polymerization. Deionized water (190 mL) was added to a round-bottomed flask (500 mL) and nitrogen gas was injected into the flask at 70°C. Styrene monomer (20 g) was added to the flask and the solution was stirred at 400 rpm for 1 h. The KPS aqueous solution made by dissolving KPS (0.2 g) in distilled water (10 mL) was slowly injected into the flask over 6 h. The polymerization reaction was terminated by quenching to 0°C. The synthesized colloidal PS spheres were centrifuged and washed several times, and the products were purified through dialysis over 7 days using a cellulose tubular membrane.

2.4. Preparation of the free-standing GNS/PBT nanocomposite film: The aqueous dispersions of the monodisperse PS spheres and the bead milled GNS were mixed under vigorous stirring, and then the solution was cast on an aluminium substrate, which had been pre-treated with UV light for 30 min for cleaning and suppressing the hydrophobic nature. The voids between the PS spheres were then infiltrated with GNS via bar casting. The PS spheres, which acted as a template for the 3D mesoporous GNS framework, were removed by calcination under N_2 atmosphere at 500°C for 4 h; the sample was then slowly cooled. The resultant 3D mesoporous interconnected GNS framework structure was

finally filled with molten CBT oligomers. Thermal treatment at 230°C for 10 min induced the ring opening and simultaneous polymerization reaction of CBT to high molecular weight polymer of PBT, and provided the free-standing GNS/PBT nanocomposite film.

2.5. Characterization: SEM images of samples adhered to a carbon tape were obtained on a JEOL 6701F instrument. TEM images were obtained with an FEI Tecnai instrument equipped with LaB6 anode. Samples were prepared by diluting the suspension with deionized water and pipetting a few microliters onto a holey-carbon-coated Formvar mesh grid. The topography was examined by AFM using a Digital Instruments Nanoscope III instrument; silicon tips were used in tapping mode at a resonance frequency of 320 kHz. DLS analysis was conducted by an ELS-80000 (Otsuka Electronics) instrument. Raman spectroscopy was carried out with a Bruker RFS-100/s spectrometer using 1064-nm laser excitation, and XPS spectra were recorded using a Physical Electronics 5600 X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy with monochromatic Al K α radiation and a hemispherical capacitor analyzer. Thermal conductivity was measured by laser flash analysis (LFA) at room temperature. The transferred signal initiated a thermal equilibration process in the nanocomposite specimen, which was recorded using a difference detector at rear surface and was used to evaluate the thermal diffusivity.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As illustrated in Figure 1, the fabrication procedure for the 3-D interconnected GNS-embedded nanocomposite film starts at the formation of 3-D interconnected GNS network structure; at first, GNS/PS sphere mixtures were aggregated *via* electrostatic attraction, and the following thermal treatment of the GNS/PS mixture for PS removal was contributed to form 3-D interconnected GNS framework architecture. Finally the pores of GNS framework were infiltrated with polymerizable cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT) oligomers, which can be easily converted to high molecular weight polymer matrix of polybutylene terephthalate (PBT).

In this study, the GNS was obtained by a mechanical delamination process of pristine graphite such as bead milling. Size-controlled GNS by milling was mixed with monodisperse PS spheres in aqueous solution to provide a GNS/PS mixture solution, and bar casting of the solution on a flat substrate resulted in a free standing film. Representative SEM images of the GNS/PS composite film by casting reveal the high packing density of the GNS/PS composite structure that was derived from electrostatic interaction between GNS and PS spheres along with infiltration of excess GNS into the interstitial volumes among the close-packed PS spheres (Figure 2a).

The pore size of the 3-D mesoporous GNS framework was guided by the sacrificial template of PS spheres. Our experiments used monodisperse PS spheres with mean diameters of 0.5 and 5 μm , respectively. The GNS/PS composite was fabricated by mechanical blending of monodisperse PS spheres with the size-controlled GNS in aqueous solution. The GNS/PS mixture was bar-casted on a flat substrate, and the PS components were removed by calcination under nitrogen atmosphere (Figure 2b). The resultant 3-D interconnected GNS framework structure was infiltrated with molten CBT oligomers, which provided a GNS-embedded free-standing nanocomposite film via decyclopolymerization of CBT to PBT. As shown in Figure 2c, the electron microscopic examinations revealed that the 3-D GNS framework was successfully filled with the PBT, without loss of the initial framework structure.

The thermal conductivity of the free-standing GNS/PBT nanocomposite film as a function of GNS content is shown in Figure 3. It was found that the addition of GNS to the PBT matrix resulted in the increase of thermal conductivity. Notably, when the GNS content was 9.1 wt%, the thermal conductivity of the nanocomposite film reached ca. $4.3 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, which is ca. 1,800 and 180% higher than those of neat PBT ($0.23 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) and of randomly mixed GNS (9.9 wt%) with PBT ($1.5 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), respectively. The results clearly show that the 3-D GNS framework architecture imparts a composite much higher efficiency in the thermal energy transfer than the randomly dispersed two-dimensional (2-D) GNS structure.

It should be noted that the concept of using 3-D GNS framework architecture works well as thermal energy transfer medium, even in a non-optimized state. The advantages of our approach include employing cheap and abundant carbon resources and simple fabrication procedure of

complicated 3-D mesoporous framework.

4 FIGURES

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the formation of GNS/PBT nanocomposite containing 3-D interconnected GNS framework. The highly aggregated mixture of GNS-wrapped PS spheres was transformed to 3-D interconnected GNS framework structure during thermal removal of polymer components, and the subsequent diffusion of CBT oligomers into the pore volumes of GNS framework resulted in the GNS/PBT nanocomposite during ring-opening polymerization of CBT to PBT.

Figure 2: SEM images of (a) the GNS/PS composite, (b) the 3-D mesoporous GNS framework, and (c) TEM image of the GNS/PBT nanocomposite after CBT infiltration and polymerization.

Figure 3: Thermal conductivity of the free-standing GNS/PBT nanocomposite film as a function of the GNS content. The 2-D GNS/PBT composite was prepared by simple mechanical mixing of GNS (9.9 wt%) with CBT as matrix, which were polymerized to form a composite.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A simple and effective strategy was designed and demonstrated to fabricate a 3-D GNS/PBT nanocomposite having outstanding thermal conductivity. A size-controlled and defect-free GNS composed of multilayered graphene sheets was easily fabricated in large quantities via wet bead milling of pristine graphite. A 3-D macroporous interconnected GNS framework structure was obtained by infiltration and then calcination of PS spheres. Most importantly, the high packing density and network of the 3-D GNS framework resulted in lower phonon boundary scattering and thereby enhanced thermal conductivity. Employing 3-D macroporous interconnected framework of 2-D graphitic sheets in polymer matrix, coupled with control of lateral size and thickness of GNS, provides a promising opportunity to obtain a novel TMM that is inexpensive, but highly outstanding for industrial applications..

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was kindly supported by a grant (Code No. 2011-0032156) from the Center for Advanced Soft Electronics under the Global Frontier Research Program of the Ministry of Science, ICT & Future Planning, Korea, and the R&D program for the technology of World Premier Materials by the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Energy, Korea, as well as the internal project of KIST. S.-S. Lee also appreciates the research grant from the KU-KIST Graduate School.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. Balandin, *Nature Materials* **30**, 2011, 569.
- [2] R. Prasher, *Proceedings of. IEEE* **94**, 2006, 1571.

- [3] a) M. Bozlar, D. He, J. Bai, Y. Chalopin, N. Mingo and S. Volz, *Advanced Materials* **22**, 2010, 1654; b) C. Zhi, Y. Bando, T. Terao, C. Tang, H. Kuwahara and D. Golberg, *Advanced Functional Materials* **19**, 2009, 1857.
- [4] a) H. Im and J. Kim, *Carbon* **49**, 2011, 3503; b) W. Zhou, S. Qi, H. Li and S. Shao, *Carbon* **48**, 2010, 1171.
- [5] a) J. W. Connell and Y. P. Sun, *Advanced Materials* **21**, 2009, 2088; b) Q. Ngo, B. A. Cruden, A. M. Cassell, G. Sims, M. Meyyappan, J. Li and C. Y. Yang, *Nano Letters* **4**, 2004, 2403.
- [6] a) R. Prasher, *Science* **328**, 2010, 185; b) M. Zhou, T. Lin, F. Huang, Y. Zhong, Z. Wang, Y. Tang, H. Bi, D. Wan and J. Lin, *Advanced Functional Materials* **23**, 2013, 2263.
- [7] K.-Y. Shin, J.-Y. Hong and J. Jang, *Advanced Materials* **23**, 2011, 2113.
- [8] J. H. Seol, I. Jo, A. L. Moore, L. Lindsay, Z. H. Aitken, M. T. Pettes, X. Li, Z. Yao, R. Huang, D. Broido, N. Mingo, R. S. Ruoff and L. Shi, *Science* **328**, 2010, 213.
- [9] S. Stankovich, D. A. Dikin, G. H. Dommett, K. M. Kohlhaas, E. J. Zimney, E. A. Stach, R. D. Piner, S. T. Nguyen and R. S. Ruoff, *Nature* **2006**, 442, 282.
- [10] S. H. Lee, H. W. Kim, J. O. Hwang, W. J. Lee, J. Kwon, C. W. Bielawski, R. S. Ruoff and S. O. Kim, *Angewante Chemie International Edition* **122**, 2010, 10282.
- [11] a) Q. Liang, X. Yao, W. Wang, Y. Liu and C. P. Wong, *ACS Nano* **5**, 2011, 2392.